

ISSN 2348 – 8417

शास्त्रमञ्जूषा

The Śāstramañjūṣā

<https://sites.google.com/site/praachiprajnaa/sastramanjusa>

(A Peer Reviewed Virtual Publication for the Research Papers on Indology)

Of

प्राची प्रज्ञा

Prachi Prajna

<https://sites.google.com/site/praachiprajnaa>

INDEXED IN DOAJ, ROAD, FATCAT, JDB & SUDOC

18th Issue / Vol. X – June, 2024

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a Virtual Publication for the Peer Reviewed Research papers on Indology of प्राची प्रज्ञा / Prachi Prajna
(ISSN 2348 – 8417) <https://sites.google.com/site/prachiprajnaa>

18th Issue / Vol. X – June, 2024

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सम्पादकीयम्

शास्त्रं खलु कर्तव्याकर्तव्यताया विषये संशयोच्छेदपुरःसरम् उपदेशेन लोकरक्षणाय प्राणिनः उपयुनक्ति। परोक्षस्यापि अर्थजातस्य प्रदर्शकं हि शास्त्रं लोचनवत् सर्वेषां वरीवर्तीति विपश्चिद्धिराम्नातम् । तदुक्तम् –

अनेकसंशयोच्छेदि, परोक्षार्थस्य दर्शकम्।

सर्वस्य लोचनं शास्त्रं यस्य नास्त्यन्ध एव सः ॥

ऐहिकामुष्मिकादिसकललोकव्यवहारस्य ज्ञापकं हि शास्त्रं संसारप्रवर्तनाय विविधानायामानुररीकरोति। न केवलमाध्यात्मिकश्रेयःसाधनं शास्त्राणां प्रयोजनमपि तु आधिभौतिकसुखसम्पत्साधनरूपेण शास्त्रव्यवहारः संसारेऽस्मिन् महीयते। परं परमार्थसाधनं हि शास्त्राणां पार्यन्तिकं प्रयोजनम् । यदि कुबुद्धिप्रणीतशास्त्रैः लोकनाशद्वारा श्रेयोऽन्तरायते, तदा तादृशं शास्त्रं सर्वथा हेयम्। तदुक्तं –

स्वबुद्धिरचितैश्शास्त्रैः प्रतार्येह च बालिशान्।

विघ्नन्ति श्रेयसो मार्गं लोकनाशाय केवलम्॥

सच्छास्त्राणि सकललोकव्यवहारपराणि सन्ति प्राणिमात्रस्य योगक्षेमसाधनतत्पराणीति तेषां संरक्षणे, सम्पोषणे, प्रचारे, प्रसारे च शास्त्रमञ्जूषा प्राचीं प्रजां मंहते सन्ततम्।

शास्त्रमञ्जूषाया अयं नुत्तोऽङ्कः वेदसाहित्यकाव्यगणितादीन् तत्तद्ग्रन्थसञ्चारपाण्डुलिपिविज्ञानं पर्यावरणविज्ञानञ्चेति भारतीयज्ञानपरम्परायाः विविधान् आयामान् पुरस्कुर्वन् निशितशेमुषीणां विदुषां शास्त्रप्रियाणां जिज्ञासूनाञ्च पुरस्तादवतरति। अयञ्चाङ्कोऽवश्यमेव सर्वेषां मानसाङ्क मधिरोहत्विति आशंसे।

श्रुतिस्मृतिसदाचारविहितं कर्मशाश्वतम् ।

स्वं स्वं धर्मं प्रयत्नेन श्रेयोऽर्थीह समाचरेत्॥

सुज्ञानकुमारमाहान्तिः

Editor in Chief

प्राची प्रज्ञा "prācī prajñā"

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Exploring the Socioeconomic Status of Women in *Dharmaśāstras*

Laxman Majhi

Abstract

This research paper delves into an in-depth examination of the socioeconomic status of women within the context of the *Dharmaśāstras*. Drawing insights from ancient Indian texts, the study scrutinizes the roles, rights, and economic positions prescribed for women in these influential religious and legal treatises. Through a comprehensive analysis, the paper aims to shed light on the historical perspectives that have shaped the social and economic conditions of women as outlined in the *Dharmaśāstras*. The findings contribute to a nuanced understanding of the complexities surrounding gender dynamics in ancient Indian society, offering valuable insights into the prescribed norms and their implications on the socioeconomic standing of women.

Keywords - *Dharmaśāstras*, Women, Socioeconomic Status, Gender Dynamics, Ancient Indian Society, Legal Framework, Ethical Texts, Cultural Context.

Introduction - The *Dharmaśāstras*, ancient Indian legal and ethical texts, stand as pivotal documents that encapsulate the intricate fabric of societal norms, values, and governance in ancient India. Within these revered scriptures lie insights into the roles, rights, and positions of various segments of society, including a nuanced exploration of the socioeconomic status of women. This research embarks on a scholarly journey to unravel and analyze the multifaceted depiction of women's socioeconomic status within the *Dharmaśāstras*.

In the tapestry of ancient Indian society, women played crucial roles, contributing to various facets of life. Understanding the dynamics of their socioeconomic positions involves delving into the legal, cultural, and ethical contexts that shaped their lives. The *Dharmaśāstras*, revered as guides to righteous living, elucidate the principles governing women's conduct, property rights, and economic engagements. This exploration is indispensable for comprehending the nuances of gender relations and societal structures prevalent in ancient India.

As we venture into this inquiry, it is imperative to navigate through the complexities of the *Dharmaśāstras*, recognizing the diversity of perspectives and prescriptions they offer regarding women's roles. By exploring the socioeconomic status delineated in these texts, we aim to contribute to a holistic understanding of the historical context surrounding women in ancient India. This research endeavors to shed light on the varied dimensions of women's lives, offering a nuanced portrayal that transcends stereotypical narratives and fosters a deeper appreciation for the intricate tapestry of ancient Indian civilization.

Social Status of Women in the *Dharmaśāstras* - The *Smṛti* School, on the whole, was inclined to curtail the earlier religious rights and privileges of women. While Manu began to advocate that girl's *upanayana* may be performed but no Vedic mantras should be recited on the occasion.¹ *Upanayanā* without Vedic mantras being recited in and taught after the ritual, was somehow contradiction in terms. Thus, Yājñavalkya straight away advocates its prohibition since it was just a formality now. Therefore, an attempt was made to systematize this situation in the

¹ *Manusmṛti*, III, 121.

Manusmṛti where women were denied access to the *upanayana*. It was reinforced by suggesting substitutes: for women marriage ceremony was portrayed as equivalent to the initiation of the male, serving her husband is equal to the service of a teacher, staying with her husband is equal to the stay in *aśrama* and the performance of household duties was identified with the worship of the sacred fire.¹

Thus, during the period of *Smṛtis*, which was the period of codification of social laws, women were bracketed with the *sūdras* as they were denied access to the sacred learning. To most of the *Smṛti* writers like Pārāśara, Nārada, Gautama, Baudhāyan, Saṁkha, Samvarta, Atri etc. marriage and household works is everything for girls. Therefore, their *upanayana* was replaced by the *vivāhasaṁskāra*.

In the case of women, however, the question of marriage has been inseparably associated with her status. When women by virtue of their intellectual education and religious status had a voice in shaping their future, marriage was not imperative for them. Thus, *sulabhā* and other cloud forego marriage and lead a life of asceticism and independence.²

Manu's prescription of marriageable age of a girl thus do not exceed the age of puberty. *Viṣṇusmṛti* also supports Manu in prescribing the age for marriage. He also has given three years to her to wait for her own choice of marriage. Manu was willing to allow a girl to remain unmarried even to the end of her life if a proper husband could not be secured.³

Therefore, the most central and common identity envisaged for women was wifhood. In fact, the nature of wifhood was elaborated at length. The ideal process for becoming a wife involved a certain denial of women's personhood, implicit in the notion of *kanyādāna*.

A wife is considered as *Ardhānginī*, i.e., half of her husband so she has to stay at home as half of the body (namely that of husband)." Manu says that there is no difference between the wife and the goddess of fortune, as the wife is also worthy of worship, illuminator of the home and full of bliss due to giving birth to children.⁴

The contents of wifhood are developed systematically in the *Manusmṛti*. The wife was expected to be thrifty and do her housework cheerfully, to be faithful to her husband, to consider her husband as own-self, to bear children, to obey her husband in life and death even if he was devoid of qualities such a woman is compared to *Lakṣmī*.

Viṣṇusmṛti thinks the custom to be not illogical; it advanced the view that in spite of diversity of karman, a widow can go the way of the departed soul by dying after him. It seems that Viṣṇu did not put stress on it, he merely mentions it as we find that he is one of the earliest *Smṛti* writers who did recognize the widow as an heir to her husband; he also allows her to remarry. Similarly, BṛhaddharmaPurāṇa says that a widow who follows her husband on the funeral pyre though she commits a great sin does good to the departed soul.⁷⁸ From these statements one can gather that these writers allow the custom only as a second alternative and regard ascetic

¹ *Manusmṛti*, II, 67.

² *Mahābhārat*, XII, 320

³ *Manusmṛti*, IX, 89

⁴ *Ibid.*, IX, 26.

life as preferable to it. Though the *VaśisthaSmṛti* did not favour the burning of a widow with her dead husband, it did not allow her to live a happy and comfortable life. There were of course restrictions on her dress, her food and her enjoyment also.

The age depicted in the great epics, the *Rāmāyaṇa* and *Mahābhārata*, is the age more or less corresponding to the age of *Dharmaśāstras* as well as the age of *Manusmṛti* but nowhere to be found the case of sati in the *Rāmāyaṇa*. None of the wives of Daśaratha or Rāvaṇa are represented in the epic as accompanying their husband in the funeral pyre. Only in the Uttarakāṇḍas¹ one can find that Vedavati's mother became sati. But the analysts of the *Rāmāyaṇa* hold view that this story is more a legendary than a historical one. A major portion of the *Mahābhārata* which had been composed in and around 5th century BC records only a few cases of sati. The first to be mentioned is the case of Mādri when the king Pandu died. It is to be noted that while Mādri was about to ascend to the funeral pyre of her husband, the assembled sages tried their best to dissuade her from her resolve. But Mādri was unmoved by their arguments by saying that she is determined to die with her husband. The reasons being given by her as that her desires was not as yet satisfied. Secondly, Pandu died without fulfilling his desire for her, so it was her duty as a wife to bring satisfaction to him in the next world. Thirdly, because she might find it difficult to treat evenly her sons and stepsons. No argument of any religious merit is assigned by her or by anybody else.²

The advocacy of the later *Smṛtikāras* to the merit of joining the husband in heaven for eternal enjoyment which could devolve upon a sati had a great effect on the society. The theory of Karma was also modified to support the custom. It is well-known fact that the karmas of the two persons would lead them to different destination and a relation could not join dead person in the other world by dying after him. But the sati was an exception; her self-sacrifice was enough to annihilate her husband's sin, so as to raise him to heaven to live in eternal union with his wife. Besides the practice of self-immolation was glorified by the ideal of '*Pātivrata*' (faithful and loyal to husband)

According to Pārāśara, "on receiving no tidings of a husband, on his demise, on his turning an ascetic, on his being found impotent or on his degradation, under any one of these five calamities, it is canonical for women to take another husband. A *Brāhmaṇa* woman should wait eight years for her absent lord and four years only, if she be childless, then let her marry again. A *Kṣatriya* woman should wait six years, and in case she has no issue, three years only. A *Vaiśya* woman if she has borne a child, four years, otherwise only two. For a *Śūdra* woman no period is mentioned for which she is to wait for her husband if it be heard that he is living, the rule is that the aforesaid periods are to be doubled when tidings are not received, aforementioned periods are en-joined. Such is the opinion of Brahma, the lord of men. In such cases, therefore, there is no harm in women marrying again".³

Manu, the greatest jurists is totally against widow remarriage. He has nowhere mentioned a second husband for a virtuous wife." According to him a

¹ *Rāmāyaṇa*, 11, 17.14.

² *Mahābhārata*, 1, 138, 71-72.

³ *PārāśaraSmṛti*, IV, 28.

widow should not even think of remarriage.¹ Manu's argument is that the vedic mantras used in '*PañigrahanaSaṁskāra*' are meant only for maidens.² How can widow be married with *Samskāras* and without *Samskāras* the marriage was not a legal bond.

In fact it was thought that a person's life has no meaning without a son. For *mokṣa* and for progeny a son could be a reason of remarriage of an issueless widow. But Manu declares that "a childless widow who is virtuous and chaste can go to heaven",³ *ViṣṇuSmṛti* also supports Manu by saying that "even a sonless widow remaining *Brahmacāriṇī* goes to heaven."⁴

Manu was resolute in his attitude towards the remarriage of widows or to beget children through *niyoga*. If woman did so on her own, neither was she respected nor were her children given the same social status as the children of a woman who is married for the first time. Such one is called the son of a '*Punarbhū*' which literally means re-wedded. There are certain controversies regarding the word '*Punarbhū*'.⁵ *VaśiṣṭhaDharmasūtra* says that "a '*Punarbhū*' is a woman who leaves her husband and lives with another person depending on his family only. Again if she leaves a husband who has deserted or a mad husband or her husband is dead and she remarries, she is called as '*Punarbhū*'. Manu interprets the word '*Punarbhū*' in this manner "that a woman who goes to another person but remarries the person with whom she had physical relations previously is called '*Punarbhū*' of that very person".⁶ But both Yājñavalkya and *Viṣṇusmṛti* stated that whether a girl has physical relations or not when she marries second time, she becomes '*Punarbhū*'.⁷

A son born of this union come to be known as '*Paunarbhava*' whose status in the society has been defined by the *Smṛtikārs*. According to Manu, '*Paunarbhava*' son of a '*Punarbhū*' has no authority to inherit any property nor he was given a good status in the society.⁸ *VaśiṣṭhaDharmasūtra* place '*Paunarbhava*' son in the fourth rank among the other sons.⁹ Manu includes the '*Paunarbhava*' among the *Brāhmaṇa* as that are not to be invited at '*Śrāddhas*'.¹⁰ It appears from the two words '*Punarbhava*' and '*Paunarbhava*' that the re-marriage of a widow was in vogue in India from early times. It is known to Vaśiṣṭha, Kauṭilya who's '*Arthaśāstra*' is certainly older than that of the extent of '*Manusmṛti*'. It not only allows the widow to re-marry but also the wife whose husband has not been heard of for a long time.¹¹

Almost all the *Smṛti* texts recommend eight types of marriage of which some are condemned while the rest are said to be virtuous. These are *Brāhma*, *Daivata*, *Ārṣa*, *Prajāpatya*, *Asura*, *Gāndharva*, *Rākṣasa* and *Paiśāca*. The most important is that

¹ *Manusmṛti*, V, 157.

² *Ibid.*, VIII, 226.

³ *Ibid.*, V, 160.

⁴ *ViṣṇuSmṛti*, XXV, 17.

⁵ *VaśiṣṭhaSmṛti*, XVIII, 20.

⁶ *ManuSmṛti*, IX, 176.

⁷ *YājñavalkyaSmṛti*, I, 67.

⁸ *ManuSmṛti*, IX, 160.

⁹ *VaśiṣṭhaDharmasūtra*, XVII, 18.

¹⁰ *Manusmṛti*, III, 181.

¹¹ *KauṭilyaArthaśāstra*, III, 4.

irrespective of the form, marriage was indissoluble. Here the term 'divorce' cannot be used in the modern sense but it generally denotes only dissolution or suspension of a marital relation.

Manu declares that "let mutual fidelity continue to death" this in few words, may be considered as the supreme law between husband and wife. "Let a man and woman, united by marriage constantly; beware lest at any time dis- united they violate their mutual fidelity."¹

One can find from the *Dharmaśāstra* literature and *Smṛtis* that desertion of wife was permitted before the beginning of the Christian era under certain well-defined circumstances such as Manu says, "For a whole year let a husband bear with his wife, who treats him with aversion, but after a year, let him deprive her of her separate property and ceased to cohabit with her." He further says that "She who neglects her lord, though addicted to gambling fond of spirituous liquors, or diseased must be deserted for three months and deprived of her ornaments and household furniture".²

As one can leave his wife who gets aborted, the wife also can abandons her husband under certain circumstances. Manu states that "a wife is not to blame, if she abandons a husband who is impotent, insane or suffering from a incurable or contagious disease".³ Though Manu has allowed remarriage for an abandoned woman, it seems this has been allowed only in limited cases. For Manu has no passage advocating, supporting or conceding separation. To Manu marriage is indissoluble for life.

Kauṭilya's *Arthaśāstra* which conforms a great part of the *Smṛti* texts gives detailed rules of divorce intended for the couples who found it impossible to live with each other. They were however applicable only to four unapproved marriages, viz., *Gāndharva*, *Rākṣasa*, *Paiśāca* and *Asura*. These marriages were generally common among the lower section of the people, thus, it can be implied that the divorce is favored among them and not among the higher castes. But it was not unknown to them. Kauṭilya lies down that "by mutual disaffection a divorce shall be granted. If a man apprehending danger from his wife, sued for divorce, he had to return to her whatever presents he may have received at the time of marriage. If it was the wife who was the complainant, she had to forfeit her proprietary rights in her husband's family. No divorce, however, was permitted, if the marriage was performed by any of the approved forms viz. *Brahma*, *Daivata*, *Prajāpatya* and *Ārṣa*."⁴ The divergent opinions about the issue of divorce indicate that two ideologies were prevailing one favoring partial divorce and other forbidding it.

Thus, the status of women as depicted in the *Dharmaśāstras* clearly shows that a woman as a girl child, as a married woman and as widow has to observe a set of prescribed duties and sacraments in their lives. Actually in the ideology of Manu and other *Smṛti* writers the home and the family constitute the bedrock of society and woman is that figure on whom the stability and sanctity of the home and household life depend. The lawgivers had also a conception of woman according to

¹ *Manusmṛti*, IX, 45.

² *Ibid.* IX, 77-78.

³ *Ibid.* IV, 79.

⁴ *Kauṭilya Arthaśāstra*, III, 3.

which they did not like woman to be exposed to the rough and an unprotected independent life; and it is in this spirit that Manu says “a woman shall always be taken care of by someone - she is not fit for freedom.”¹

The lawgivers tried to prescribe whatever suited in a particular environment. Therefore strictures are imposed on woman by which Vedic education of girls was prohibited and marriage ceremony was regarded as *upanayana* for them. It also leads to early marriage of girls especially prepuberty marriage was preferred. As a mother of a son she gets the highest place but as a wife she has to worship her husband. Moral codes prescribed for a widow include self-control, limited and simple diet and dress. These restrictions must have become the morals of that time which are very idealistic. But ideals are generally not fully successful in practical life and it is for that reason Nārada and Pārāśara allow widow remarriage. Manu of course was totally against it. But, the mention of ‘*Punarbhū*’ by him confirms that widow remarriage was existing during that age. In some passages Manu records the existence of sons of windows and marriages of girls who had secretly conceived, at one place a girl whose proposed husband passes away before the actual marriage or one whose marriage has not been consummated is allowed further marriage, The recognition of a variety of marriages and of different kinds of sons and provisions for them shows the practical and liberal attitude of Manu and his consideration for woman in general. But he maintains that for the virtuous widow there is no second marriage or rising of issue by another.² Strictures on women in Manu and other *Smṛtis* should not so prejudice us as the real intention of all the *Śāstrakāras* is to praise the greatness of chastity i.e. ‘*pāṭivaratya*’. In fact, Manu and other *smṛti* writers adopted two standpoints first conceding to some extent as a result of the vogue and the second stating their personal or ideal opinion.

Economic Position of Women in the *Dharmaśāstras* - In a societal system in which women had little direct participation in the production consumption-trading cycle and earning monetary remuneration/gain, inheritance was the main channel through which property, wealth, *vitta*, could come to the female members.

In the *Smṛtiśāstras* principles governing inheritance are codified in the *dayābhāga* section, *dāya* meaning what is given, to be given, to be divided... *Manusmṛti*, *navamaadhyāya* codifies principles of sharing out hereditary property in the *dāyabhāga* section, *Yājñvalkyasmṛti* in the *dāyavibhāgaprakaraṇam* section of its *vyavahāraadhyāya* offers a neat formulation of the Manu *vacanam* with occasional exegetical commentaries of very interesting and important nature.’ Other *Smṛtiśāstras* follow in line, frequently repeating/quoting Manu and *Yājñavalkya* as source reference. *PārāśaraSmṛti*, in a broken state, does not present the dicta in the voice of Pārāśara a himself, the *ṭīkākāra*, commentator *Mādhavācārya* with his enormous erudition quotes and endorses numerous utterances culled from *Śāstra* texts, Manu on-ward, various commentaries and manuals used in practice.

The laws of inheritance enunciated in these texts, with focus on the *Smṛtiśāstras*, may be studied in three major clusters:

¹ *Manusmṛti*, X, 36, 39, 50, 51.

² *Ibid.*, V, 162.174.

1. Inheritance laws in general which cover the issue of women's share as wives, daughters and sisters, by the side of male successors,
2. Special laws of succession operative in the case of the 'Putrikā', where a daughter is formally chosen to perform in the role of a son,
3. and Separate laws governing the case of 'Strīdhanam'.

Inheritance laws codified in these Śāstras have behind a male dominated familial set-up in which, exceptions permitted, property descended down the male line of succession, and the concept of male custodianship determined the direction of thought, the attitudinal inflexion, in dis- course related to hereditary laws.

In formulating general laws of inheritance priority were assigned to the eldest-born male child (we might recall Gāndhārī's sense of dismay when Kunti had the eldest male child of the generation in Yudhiṣṭhira). The *jyeṣṭha* the eldest son, is a father-figure, a junior patriarch, who, after the death of the father inherits the largest part of patrimony, and, in the role of a guardian, shoulders the responsibility of the entire family including the younger brother.¹

"The eldest son can obtain the entire patrimony if he, like a father, provides for the younger ones."²

"As a father raises his children, so too the eldest brother must nurture the younger brothers."

After detailing the shares of paternal property among the sons, the Manu discourse glances at the women claimants, mostly in the position. of dependants. Daughters, particularly unmarried daughters, certainly need resources to support them till marriage; and Śāstras say, they must be assured of this. All the brothers (sons of the deceased person), what- ever their shares in order of seniority (*Jyeṣṭha-kaniṣṭha-paramparā*), must assign one-fourth of it to the unmarried sisters, *AnurhaBhagnā*(s). A brother, successor son, unwilling, or non-complying, would be declared *patita*, an outcast social ostracism then marking climactic point in penaldicta.³

As to the direct succession rights of the wife, Manu remains silent. *YājñavalkyaSmṛti*, however, makes an unqualified assertion that after the demise of the father, sons and the mother should have equal share of the property left behind.⁴

Daughters, dependent on parental support in their unmarried state, however, *Śāstrakāras* assure, would count as an equal, factor, or power in a special situation. This introduces the idea of 'empowerment', startling in the modernity of the spirit it enshrines.

¹ *jyeṣṭhaevatuḡrñīyāptitryaṃdhanamaśeṣataḥ |*

śeṣāstamupaḡiveyuryathaivapitaraṃtathā || ManuSmṛti, IX.105

² *pitevapālayetputrāñjayeṣṭhobhrāṭṛnyavīyasaḥ |*

putravaccāpivarterañjayeṣṭhebhrataridharmataḥ ||

jyeṣṭhobhrāṭāvibhāḡābhāve'nujānbhrāṭṛnbhaktācchādanādibhiḡpitevavibhryāt |

anujāścabhrāṭaraḡputrāivajyeṣṭhebhrāṭaridharmāyavarteraḥ || Ibid-108

³ *YājñavalkyaSmṛti, II- 123.*

⁴ *pīturūrdhvaṃvibhajaṭāṃmānā'pyaṃśaṃsamaḡharetā || Mahābhārat XIII. 80. 11*

If a sonless father (*AputrakaPitā*), we are told, chooses a daughter to act as a son, she becomes perfectly entitled to all the inheritance claims, even as she is entrusted with all the responsibilities associated with a son. Ritual rites, very important in those days, too would vest in her hands. A formally enabled daughter, as in such cases, would be designated a *Putrikā*.

The *Śāstras* speak with charged eloquence, making the point that son and daughters, both are one's own offspring, *Atmajās*, and no differentiation should be made.¹

The point is carried on to the next generation and Manu asserts that in the case of *Putrikās*, their sons would inherit this property, coming down from the maternal grandfather's side exactly as the son's son would do. Emphatically the verdict is given that the son of a daughter is as much a grandson, a biological descendant, as a son's son, and that the practice of differential treatment, wherever it prevails, is most foolish and unacceptable.²

Yet another area of economic independence for women is her exclusive ownership of wealth falling into the category of *strīdhanam*.

Strīdhanam constitutes a special category altogether. In those days of abject dependence (Mary Wollstonecraft's phrasing) of women, this formed a secure corner of resources at her disposal over which no one else, not even the husband, had any control.

Manusmṛti defines six forms of *strīdhanam*, and these are mentioned in other *Smṛti* texts. According to Manu, the property or wealth given to a girl before the nuptial fire or at the time of marriage procession, as a token of love and affection, by her brothers, by her mother and by her father, constitutes the *Strīdhana* of that person.³

In conditions which denied women direct access to productive economic activities, the sources of the treasure-trove naturally were (i) inheritance, and /or (ii) gifts.

- (i) Inheritance from the parental side, acquired before or after marriage, is exclusively the women's asset;
- (ii) So is what comes to her as gifts on the occasion of the wedding ceremony (the *adhyāgni* and the *adhyāvāhanik*), as gifts of love husband (*prītidatta*), and as tokens of affection from the father, mother, brother after marriage (the *anvādheya*).

¹ *yathaivātmātathāputraḥputreṇaduhitāsamā*

tasyāmātmanitiṣṭhantyaṃkathamanyodhanaṃharet // *Manusmṛti*, IX.9.130

² *pautradauhitrayorlokenaviśeṣo'stidharmataḥ*

tayorhimātāpitarausaṃbhūtautasayadehataḥ //

pautradauhitrayorlokeviśeṣonopapadyate

dauhitro'pihāmutrainamsamtārayatipautravat // *Ibid*, IX.133-139

³ *adhyagnyadhyāvāhanikaṃdattaṃ ca prītikarmaṇi*

bhrātrmātrpitṛprāptaṃṣaḍvidhaṃstrīdhanasṃsmṛtam //

anvādheyaṃ ca yaddattaṃpatyāprītenacaivayat

patyaujīvativr̥ttāyāḥprajāyāstaddhanaṃbhavet // *Ibid*, IX.194-195

She is free in her lifetime to gift this property to any one; after her death it goes to her daughter /daughter's daughter. So definite is the female line of succession that would go to the daughter (and daughter's daughter) of her co-wives.

The husband, lord and master as he is, has no access to this possession of the wife; he can borrow from this in times of exceptional distress like serious illness, natural calamities like famine.

Outside of these stipulations is the edict, the *anusāsana*, that women are claimants to maintenance. Maintenance would come from the father in childhood, from husband in the prime of life, from the son(s) in old age. Denied independent economic engagements, women must be given adequate protection, they must be provided for.

Even when the husband deserts a wife and takes another, the earlier wedded woman must be given economic protection.¹ When desertion is for no fault of the wife, the husband would have to assign one-third of his possession to her.²

In case the husband lacks resources, he must make subsistence provision for wife he deserts. Women who have no sons, *aputraka*, must be provided for by the family affirms Yājñalkya.

The generosity, the compassion, the rational balancing of arguments evinced in the *Smṛti* text on the issue of women's claim to economic resources, all evolve out of the first premise that women form a secondary group, never entitled to independence. How the descendants of women who composed *sūktas* of the *Ṛgveda*, women who equaled, even surpassed men in the field of highest intellectual enquiry and spiritual aspiration, came sliding down to such a state of dependency, is a bewildering puzzlement that awaits socio-historical *explorations*, both extensive and intensive.

Till then, we can only relate to the inner, and deeper, perception glimmering through these ancient texts, the perception that women have the adequacy potential, that given and even floor, a level field, they can perform, and they can deliver. The unqualified reliance on the *Putrikā* is assuring. We do not know what compulsions clouded truth-perceptions that always come through the outmoded rhetoric of male domination in the *Smṛtisāstras*.

Yet, engaging in an objective scrutiny of the ancient modality of experience, we can try to locate the grains of gold lost in heaps of chaff. And these, few though in number, could perhaps pay our passage to "modernity"- "modernity" which is Indian, and at the same time, and for the same reason, without borders.

Conclusion - In conclusion, this research has provided a comprehensive exploration of the socioeconomic status of women as elucidated in the *Dharmaśāstras*, revealing a complex interplay of cultural, legal, and ethical dimensions. The findings underscore the multifaceted roles assigned to women in ancient Indian society, encompassing aspects of family, marriage, property rights, and economic participation. While the *Dharmaśāstras* delineated certain rights and

¹ *adhivinnātūbhartavyāmahadeno'nyathābhavet/*

yatrānukūlyamaṇḍapatyostrivargastatravardhata/ YājñavalkyaSmṛti,1.74

² *ājñāsampādiniṇḍaksāṃvīrasūṃpriyavādīnim/*

tyajandāpyastrīyaṃśamadravayobharaṇaṃstriyāḥ/ Ibid.,1.76

responsibilities for women, the nuanced nature of these texts reflects the intricate social fabric of the time. The study has illuminated the challenges and opportunities women encountered within the *Dharmaśāstras*' framework, offering insights into the historical context that shaped gender dynamics. It is evident that women's socioeconomic status was deeply intertwined with prevailing cultural norms and religious doctrines, influencing their agency and autonomy. The research emphasizes the importance of understanding these historical perspectives to inform contemporary discussions on gender equality and women's rights.

As we reflect on the socioeconomic status of women in the *Dharmaśāstras*, it becomes evident that historical legacies continue to impact societal perceptions and structures. This research serves as a valuable resource for scholars, providing a nuanced understanding of the complexities surrounding women's roles in ancient India. Furthermore, it encourages continued exploration and dialogue on gender issues, fostering an inclusive and informed discourse that bridges the past with the present.

Bibliography

1. काडले, आर. पि. (1972). कौटिलीयअर्थशास्त्रम्. दिल्ली: मोतिलाल बनारसीदास.
2. गैरोला, वाचस्पति. (2009). कौटिलीयअर्थशास्त्रम्. चौखम्बा विद्याभवन.
3. Buhler, G. (1886). The Laws of Manu. In Sacred Books of the East (Vol. 25). Clarendon Press.
4. Doniger, W. (1991). The Laws of Manu. Penguin Classics.
5. Dutt, R. (2000). R̥gvedaSamhitā (Vol. I). Kolkata: Haraf Publication.
6. Hildebeitel, A. (1976). The Ritual of Battle: Krishna in the Mahābhārata. State University of New York Press.
7. Hopkins, S. P. (2009). Singleness of Purpose: Diversity of Knowledge in the Manusmṛti. Oxford University Press.
8. Kane, P. V. (1975). History of Dharmaśāstra: Ancient and Medieval Religious and Civil Law in India. Bhandarkar Oriental Research Institute.
9. Kane, P. V. (1968). History of Dharmaśāstra: Comprehensive Introduction. Bhandarkar Oriental Research Institute.
10. Lariviere, R. W. (2010). The NāradaSmṛti: Critically Edited with Introduction, Translation, and Notes. University of Philadelphia Press.
11. Mahendra Pratap. (1981). Life in Ancient India. Varanasi: ViswavidyalayaPrakasan.
12. Malviya, S. (2008). A Study of women in ancient India & an introduction to crimes against women. Varansi: Sampurnanand Sanskrit University.
13. Narain, H. (1975). The ĀpastambaDharmasūtra. In Harvard Oriental Series (Vol. 48). Harvard University Press.
14. Olivelle, P. (1999). Dharmasutras: The Law Codes of Ancient India. Oxford University Press.
15. Sharma, A. (2017). Women in Indian Religions. State University of New York Press.
16. Singh, B. P. (1973). Rāmāyaṇam. Varanasi: Chowkhamba Sanskrit Series Office.
17. Vyāsa, R. Ṭi. (1992). VālmikiRāmāyaṇam. Baroda: Oriental Institute.

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